

**THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE
CONCEPT OF SOCIAL ORGANIZATIONS**

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Abstract: This article covers such aspects as the essence of the concept of social organization, its importance in the life of society and individuals, the development process of social organizations, the approaches of scientists and the types, characteristics of social organizations.

Keywords: social organization, formal, informal organization, kidney, production organization, social organizations.

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Social organizations form one of the main "cells" of the social structure, which, like social institutions, ensure the stable development of society as a whole system. Social organization (lot. "organizo" - to organize) is a large compound that, on the basis of the division of Labor and obligations of people, groups and the presence of a management structure, unites to solve one or another task, carries out coordinated activities based on the internal discipline of society.

It is difficult to imagine human life and activity without social organizations along with certain social groups. An extremely important phenomenon associated with his life should be noted - birth, marriage or death! For this, a person turns to certain organizations. Also, in the daily life of a person, he has direct contact with several government organizations, such as education, sanitation, utilities, environmental control and the like. Anthony Giddens noted that "if we want to communicate with others by phone or letter throughout our lives, if we want our game to be bright and warm, if we want to read newspapers and magazines, watch TV, hear the radio, get information and have fun, we will always remain dependent on organizations" [1].

Currently, there are different approaches to the issue of social organization, which is recognized in several meanings. Firstly, the organization is an integral part of society and is interpreted as an association of people who regulate the structure of a particular social object, and secondly, those who are engaged in the management and control of the activities of people with the help of their well-defined norms.

In the process of researching social organizations, many scientists tried to interpret their views. Specifically N.Smelzer: "a social organization is a social group formed to achieve certain goals" [2]. A.I.Prigogine states that "a social organization arises at the time of achieving certain common goals, achieving individual goals, or vice versa, and achieving individual goals by promoting common goals" [3].

The social organization basically performs the functions of creating the initial conditions for people to participate in social relations in the social system, ensuring the socialization of individuals by mastering the norms and values of morality in the social system, controlling the individual behavior and directions, as well as the non-deviation of their relationships from the framework of the existing system. Society treats a social organization as a means of implementing certain economic, social, political and ideological goals. In history, social organizations have evolved under the influence of traditional traditions. It was then established by the authorities to achieve certain goals and placed in special buildings.

At present, it is not so difficult to realize the importance of social organizations for the functioning of our lives. Until today's global Development, people had their basic needs in a primitive way, such as simple living, raising children, work and rest, satisfied with relatives and neighbors, as well as within the neighborhood. Meanwhile, many of our needs can also be met by those we have never met in life and who probably live thousands of kilometers away from us! In such conditions, we feel that social organizations play an extremely important role in human life and activities. The evaluation criterion for the functioning of a social organization: is related to how much people are able to use the available opportunities to enter a goal before society. Social organization limits the possibilities of people to realize their needs and interests. These restrictions are expressed in the social rules and norms adopted by these social organizations. The quality of a social organization is determined by the conditions created for the manifestation of the practical activities and characteristics of individuals in the process of its development. The person performing organizational work, the group is the subject of the social organization.

The social organization must serve to improve the integration of communities in order to solve the tasks for which it is intended. The actions and directions of members of a social organization, if they comply with social laws, lead to positive changes, that is, the correspondence of the goals promoted by social organizations with social and economic tasks in society ensures the normal development of any organization. There is a correctly chosen goal that will help to mobilize opportunities and funds in a productive way, the activities of people will expand even more. And the uncertainty of goals can negatively affect the development of society. Social organizations come in formal and informal appearances. They can

be divided into formal and informal types, depending on their role in the life of society, position, behavior and goals and objectives.

An official social organization is an association of people whose norms and rules of office are registered, governed by high-level instructions, orders, orders, and are formally formed. Any official social organization will have its own special administrative apparatus. The main task of this administrative apparatus is to coordinate the activities of its members in order to ensure the existence of the organization. The structure of a formal social organization includes the following elements: the goals and objectives of the organization, the members of the organization, the "organizers" are the link that forms and organizes management, and this feature is not necessary for large and small groups, a set of interconnected roles, that is, each person performs his own touch from the general work, rules for the system of relations between members of the organization, other organizations, surrounding communities, social groups (for example, clients) and institutions, as well as relations with the same society as a whole, is primarily intended.

The structure of a formal social organization is characterized by the following features:

1) rational, that is, on the basis of its formation and functioning, lies the principle of purposeful and useful, as well as conscious action towards a particular goal;

2) non-personal, that is, the predominance of relations in accordance with the functions established in the organization, not indifferent to the individual and personal characteristics of the members of the organization;

3) regulates and manages service relationships, that is, service-related relationships;

4) functionality, that is, directs its activities towards the necessary functional goals;

5) the presence of organizers, that is, the presence of leaders who, in order to ensure the stability of the organization, direct the relations between its members towards a single whole goal, and are constantly responsible for coordinating the effectiveness of its activities as a whole, is taken into account.

American sociologist A. Ettisoni includes 3 main types of official organizations: 1. Free organizations. This includes more public organizations, women's societies, etc. 2. Utilitarian (profitable) organizations. Cooperation, associations, firms, state institutions, etc. 3. Mandatory organizations. Correctional institutions, prison, army, etc.

The nature of formal social organizations will depend on the type of society. Because the interaction between people is developed in accordance with the laws and norms. In official organizations, the tendency to bureaucracy will be strong.

Hence, "bureaucracy" (fran. "bureau" - Bureau, office and Greek. "kratos" - power, domination) means "authority of the office". It was introduced into consumption in 1745 by the French scientist De Guerne. The word is a layer of people who are separated from the people and have specific tasks and privileges as a rule over it, denoting a management system that carries out its interests with the help of the organization sociologist M.Weber recognizes the following signs by analyzing some characteristics typical of an ideal type of bureaucracy:

First, it has a strict dependence, in which the tasks in the organization are distributed in the form of "service obligations". Bureaucracy is in the form of a pyramid, that is, from its apex to the bottom, a "chain of government" is formed, which makes it possible to make appropriate decisions. Each tier in the hierarchy controls and controls a single tier lower tier from its own.

Secondly, the rules determine the behavior of officials at all levels of the organization, but does this not mean that bureaucratic obligations are a simple and easy task? The higher the career, the more qualities the rules that apply to it cover, and the more complex they become.

Thirdly, officials are "busy" during the working day and receive a salary according to their careers. Each position owner in the hierarchy is clearly defined. Organizations expect each individual to pursue a higher career, that is, the ability to grow is carried out based on the position they hold or both.

Fourth, there is a clear boundary between the obligations of an official within the organization and the activities of its management. His personal life is strictly different from his activities at work. Fifth, none of the members of the organization can own the material resources that it manages.

M.Weber recognized bureaucracy as a major drawback, which has a strong negative impact on the activities of public life. The system of bureaucracy is associated with the administrative-command system of management. The administrative-command system of management is highly centralized and administrated in all spheres of social life, characterized by an extremely low level of political-legal culture and a violation of the principles of transparency. An example of this is the former Soviet regime.

In the Administrative-Command System, Management also includes authoritarian control elements. Authoritarian (lot. "autoritas" - authority, prestige) is a system based on unconditional subordination to the rigid governing power. Authoritarian order, that is, the unlimited power of a single ruler (monarch, dictator) who violates laws and demands unconditional obedience from the people. This order is characterized by the complete or partial abolition of the political rights and freedoms of citizens, the equalization of the ruling party to the status of the state, the liquidation of Central and local representative bodies or the

transformation of the S into puppet institutions, the de facto abolition of the principle of "distribution of power". In this case, the activities of some elements of democratic order – the electoral system, various political parties, etc.-are allowed, albeit limited.

On the basis of complementing and contrary to the shortcomings of formal organizations, the behavior and characteristics of people in it, as well as the overlap of their interests, informal social organizational ties arise. These relations are governed not on the basis of orders, orders of the state, but by people with a special reputation. In informal communication, interaction between people is carried out on the basis of faith in the correctness of the leader's recommendations and free Submission. Informal social contacts begin to operate due to the mistakes made by formal social organizations, that is, after violations occur in the holistic system.

An informal social organization is a unit of people formed on the basis of the common interests of people and the predominance of interpersonal relationships. Informal social organizations, as a unit of people who arise by themselves and for internal reasons, try to solve organizational issues in ways that differ from those specified in official laws. It is based on free Submission.

Three main features of an informal social organization can be shown: the emergence of an informal organization occurs in a sudden, unplanned way, depending on the conditions; an informal social organization will exist and operate in parallel, side by side with a formal social organization; the main feature of an informal organization-the content of interpersonal Monas-bots – is formed by informal relations.

In formal social organizations, people seek to strictly follow the mutual position in terms of career, while in informal organizations this situation varies depending on the situation. Informal organizations provide opportunities for the development and implementation of new procedures.

The following main types of social organization include: labor, production and social organizations. A labor organization is a unit of people who operate according to a certain plan to achieve a common goal and are organized in an organizational way to produce socially necessary products or provide services that are of value to their members.

Production Organization-refers only to the sphere of production of material things, where workers and employees come together for the purpose of producing material wealth. A labor organization is a broad concept in relation to a development organization, it also includes production, scientific, educational, medical, cultural and household, management and other organizations. Labor organizations operate in all spheres of society and differ from each other mainly by two criteria.

Social organizations are non-governmental and non-profit organizations united on the basis of common interests and goals of citizens. These include citizens' organizations operating in self-government, environmental, political, Sports, Leisure, charitable, cultural and other areas.

According to the degree of solidarity between social organizations: it is divided into association, cooperative, collective and corporation organizations.

Principles of activity of social organizations. Social organizations should always meet the following conditions:

- the presence of a common goal consciously set forward and the orientation of the organization's activities to achieve it;
- hierarchical (step by step) existence of legal status and roles, that is, vertical distribution of social status and roles of individuals;
- availability of requirements and rules that must be met by individuals entering the organization;
- the presence of a specialty that performs functional tasks is implied.

USED LITERATURE:

1. Энтони Гидденс. Социология. – Т., 2002. – Б. 315.
2. Смелзер Н. Социология. – Москва. 1994. –С. 189– 636.
3. Пригожин А. И. Современная социология организаций. –Москва. 1995. –С. 45.